

Human-Robot interactions and embodiment of assistive wearable robots

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Abstract—Wearable robots to assist rehabilitation is taking hold in clinical settings. Despite the advantages of robotic over traditional rehabilitation, its efficacy is disputed. This conflicting evidence is due to several factors including the lack of acceptance of the devices by end users. This pilot study aims to investigate the relationships between human and robot-related factors playing a role in human-robot integration to promote a human-centric approach in robotic rehabilitation. Ten healthy subjects were recruited and asked to walk on a 10-meter path for 10 trials while donning an assistive lower limb exoskeleton. Participants were assessed for experienced workload, anxiety, cognitive reserve, and perceived exoskeleton usability. Pre-trial anxiety levels were higher than post-trial ones ($p < 0.01$). Anxiety scores were predictive of the rated workload (Adjusted- $r^2 = 0.45$, $p = 0.02$), and of experienced effort using the exoskeleton (Adjusted- $r^2 = 0.43$, $p = 0.02$). Cognitive reserve scores were average and predictive of the exoskeleton pragmatic quality (Adjusted- $r^2 = 0.45$, $p = 0.02$). Negative correlation emerged between the workload and the hedonic component of the exoskeleton' perceived usability ($r = -0.67$, p -value = 0.03). This study highlights the connection between human-related factors (i.e., psychoaffective and cognitive) and robot acceptance. Assessing these factors jointly and considering their reciprocal interactions can help guide the design of upcoming devices, and end user selection.

Index Terms—robotic rehabilitation, psychoaffective features, cognition, robot acceptability, robotic gait training

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic technology is increasingly adopted to assist and rehabilitate various clinical populations (e.g., stroke and spinal cord injured patients) as well as in elderly assistance [1], [2]. The reason lies in the several advantages of the robotic rehabilitation compared with the traditional one: it allows high dose and high intensity tasks-specific and multisensory stimulation, which can favor behavioral restitution and reduce the burden on medical staff. However, the efficacy of robotic rehabilitation is still a matter of discussion [1], [3]. These inconsistent results may be linked to several factors including the lack of shared clear-cut criteria to set the device parameters, different neurophysiological and biomechanical features of each clinical

condition, and the absence of criteria to select patients who can benefit more from this approach. Additionally, there are still several barriers to make them efficient and beneficial in real-world scenarios: current exoskeletons are bulky, heavy, difficult to don and control, and perceived by end-users as external agents [4]. These factors together result in the lack of acceptance of the exoskeletons by end users, thus, affecting compliance with treatments and rehabilitation efficacy. Identifying the factors which play a role in human-robot integration can be fundamental to advance the development of upcoming exoskeleton devices and boost their acceptance among end users.

The current study is part of a broader project aiming to define new markers of human-robot integration (i.e., biomechanical, neurophysiological, psychological) to assess exoskeletons design and improve their capability to assist human movements. Particularly, this pilot study aimed to:

- 1) Identify the interactions between factors supposed to concur to an efficient human-robot integration.
- 2) Propose a comprehensive model to support clinicians in the selection of people more likely to benefit from robotic gait rehabilitation.

II. METHODS

A. Participants

Ten healthy volunteers (5 males) were recruited. Inclusion criteria were: age between 18 and 30 years; naïve to gait training exoskeleton use; anthropometric characteristics meeting exoskeleton requirements (i.e., height range: [150-180 cm]; weight < 90 Kg).

B. Exoskeleton (ALICE)

The exoskeleton employed in this study was the assistive lower limb-controlled exoskeleton (ALICE), available at the Intelligent Autonomous Systems Laboratory (IAS-Lab) of the University of Padova (see Fig. 1). The length of the links and

the size of the pelvis frame were manually adjusted by an expert operator to fit the body characteristics of each subject. The exoskeleton gait profile was activated by participants attempting a step with the desired leg. The exoskeleton provides additional power which complement user' leg strength needed to complete the gait trajectory.

Fig. 1. Picture of the ALICE prototype at the IAS-LAB. Technical data available on the website: <http://www.indi.global/alice>

C. Questionnaires and Clinical scales

- State and Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI-Y) [5]: STAY-Y is a 40-item self-report and validated questionnaire whose scores range from 20 to 80, with higher scores indicating higher levels of anxiety.
- Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire (CRIq) [6]: a semi-structured interview collecting information related to the participants education, working activity and leisure time.
- The NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [7]: a multi-dimensional workload assessment tool evaluating six sub-scales of the workload (i.e., mental demand, physical demand, temporal demand, performance, effort, and frustration).
- User experience questionnaire (AttrakDiff, from: <https://attrakdiff.de/index-en.html>): a questionnaire assessing exoskeleton perceived usability through 4 factors (i.e., Pragmatic quality (PQ); Hedonic quality-stimulation (HQ-S); Hedonic quality-identity (HQ-I); Attractiveness (ATT)).

D. Data Collection

Participants were asked to don the exoskeleton and walk at self-selected speed on a 10-meter walkway for 10 trials. The total time spent donning the exoskeleton, the effective time of trials execution, and the number of steps made during the trials, were collected to quantify effort and physical fatigue. Before donning the exoskeleton, participants filled-in the STAI-Y to evaluate pre-trial anxiety levels and the CRIq. At the end of the trials, participants were assessed for post-trial anxiety (STAY-Y), experienced workload (NASA-TLX) and perceived usability (AttrakDiff).

E. Statistics

Statistical significance was set at p-value < 0.05. Data distribution was tested with a Shapiro-Wilks normality test. Within group differences were evaluated with a paired sample t-test or a Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The relationships between factors were tested through the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and generalized linear models (GLMs)

III. RESULTS

A. Motor Performance

The mean total time spent donning the exoskeleton and the number of steps made are reported in Table 1.

TABLE I
MOTOR PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS

	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max
Time (min)	32	15.66	15	29	68
Number of steps	173	18.77	156	164	210

B. Questionnaires

- STAY-Y: The state anxiety levels before starting the trial were higher than the state anxiety levels post-trial (pre-trial mean (SD): 30.7 (5.94), post-trial mean (SD): 24.6 (4.69), p-value = 0.005).
- NASA-TLX: Exoskeleton-related workload was rated as “quite high” (50 % of participants). Particularly, effort, mental and physical demand obtained the highest scores, with the effort scale scores resulting significantly higher than the mental ($V = 42.5$, $p=0.02$) and physical ones ($V= 50$, $p=0.02$).
- CRIq and AttrkDiff: Cognitive reserve scores were average in 70% of participants (normative average range score [85-114]); HQ-S and ATT obtained the highest scores (HQ-S mean (SD): 1.26 (0.82); ATT mean (SD): 1.22 (0.76)). The overall hedonic dimension (i.e., HQ-S and HQ-I), resulted significantly higher than the perceived pragmatic quality (HQ mean (SD): 0.9 (1.06); PQ mean (SD): 0.03 (0.74), $W = 160.5$, $p\text{-value} = 0.01$).

C. Correlations and GLMs

Fig. 2 summarizes the tested relation between factors. GLM analysis highlighted that state anxiety levels after using the exoskeleton can predict the NASA-TLX total score (Adjusted $r^2 = 0.45$, F-statistics = 8.32, p-value = 0.02), while trait anxiety levels can predict the experienced effort (Adjusted- $r^2 = 0.43$, F-statistics = 7.71, $p=0.02$).

The cognitive reserve index could not predict the scores of the NASA-TLX but was predictive of the perceived pragmatic quality of the AttakDiff (Adjusted $r^2 = 0.45$, F-statistic = 8.52, p-value = 0.02).

The motor performance was not predictive of the NASA-TLX score, however, there was a tendency of the total time spent

Fig. 2. Dashed lines represent those relations not reaching statistical significance but showing a tendency toward it. Solid lines represent the significant relations. For the GLM analyses are reported the F-statistics and p-values, while for correlation analyses are reported correlation coefficients (r) and the p-values.

donning the exoskeleton in predicting the physical demand component of the NASA-TLX (Adjusted r^2 : 0.29, F-statistic: 4.71, p-value= 0.06) and of the total number of steps in predicting the reported exoskeleton attractiveness (Adjusted r^2 : 0.30, F-statistic: 4.89, p-value= 0.06). Negative correlation emerged between the workload and the hedonic component of the exoskeleton’ perceived usability ($r = -0.67$, p-value = 0.03).

IV. DISCUSSION

Participants demonstrated high state anxiety levels before exoskeleton use, which decrease significantly after training. This finding suggests that lack of familiarization or knowledge of the device induces unnecessary anxiety, which is not related to subjects’ trait characteristics. Higher state anxiety levels have been associated with increased perceived workload [8], which is what happened with our sample, as anxiety levels were predictive of the NASA-TLX total score. Thus, in at-risk populations, anxiety should be reduced by providing preliminary information or by allowing the participants to familiarize with the device before training itself in order to reduce the perceived workload.

The cognitive reserve was not related to the perceived workload but was instead associated with the device evaluation. Particularly, people with higher education levels tended to rate the exoskeleton as less complex but more motivating. This suggests that people with higher CRI can probably be more motivated and less intimidated in undergoing robotic rehabilitation. This is a factor to take into account when selecting patients for robotic rehabilitation, as motivation is fundamental for rehabilitation efficacy [9].

Finally, we did not find significant relations between motor

performance, experienced workload and AttrakDiff scores. However, tendencies can be observed. Particularly the total number of steps seems to be related with the perceived device attractiveness. This data can indicate that longer use of a device can be a factor increasing its acceptance, which is in line with previous literature [10].

V. CONCLUSION

This pilot study highlights the impact of cognitive and psychoaffective traits on the perceived workload and on device evaluation during exoskeleton training. Assessing these factors jointly and considering their reciprocal interactions can help developing a human-centric approach in robotic rehabilitation.

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